

Assessment of Sleep Quality among Medical Students of Udaipur: A Cross-Sectional Study**Ashish Jain¹, Chandra Prakash Sharma², Mahesh Upadhyay¹, Chandan Mal Fatehpuria², Jatin Prajapati³, Shivani Vihan³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India³PG student, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

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Abstract**Background:** Sleep plays a crucial role in the cognitive, emotional, and physical well-being of individuals, particularly medical students who face intense academic demands and irregular schedules. Poor sleep quality can adversely affect academic performance, mental health, and overall quality of life. This study aimed to assess the sleep quality and its associated factors among medical students in a tertiary care teaching institute in Udaipur, Rajasthan.**Objective:** To determine the prevalence of poor sleep quality and identify associated sociodemographic and behavioral factors among undergraduate medical students.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 206 medical students selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a pretested semi-structured questionnaire and the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) to assess sleep quality. A global PSQI score >5 indicated poor sleep. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and p-values <0.05 were used to assess associations between variables.**Results:** The prevalence of poor sleep quality was 62.6%. The mean global PSQI score was 7.3 ±3.1. The most affected PSQI components included increased sleep latency (71.8%), daytime dysfunction (67.4%), and poor subjective sleep quality (54.9%). Poor sleep quality was significantly associated with female gender (p=0.04), academic stress (p=0.001), physical inactivity (p=0.01), and screen exposure >1 hour before bed (p=0.002). Poor sleep prevalence increased with academic seniority, with interns reporting the highest rates.**Conclusion:** A significant proportion of medical students suffer from poor sleep, largely driven by academic stress and unhealthy lifestyle habits. Integrating sleep hygiene education, promoting physical activity, and limiting screen exposure may help improve sleep quality. Institutional efforts are needed to prioritize student well-being as a component of medical education.**Keywords:** Sleep quality, medical students, PSQI, stress, academic performance, cross-sectional study, Udaipur.

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Introduction

Sleep is a fundamental physiological process that plays a vital role in physical health, emotional regulation, memory consolidation, and cognitive functioning. Adequate sleep is crucial for concentration, learning, and effective decision-making—skills that are particularly essential for medical students [1,2]. However, medical education is widely acknowledged as one of the most demanding and stressful academic pursuits. Students often face an intensive curriculum, long study hours, frequent examinations, night duties, and emotional exposure during clinical postings. These challenges significantly contribute to poor

sleep hygiene and insufficient sleep duration among medical students [3]. Sleep disturbances among medical students have become a growing public health concern both globally and in India. Several studies have consistently reported a high prevalence of poor sleep quality among medical undergraduates, ranging between 50% to 70% in India alone [4,5]. Contributing factors include academic stress, screen time, poor time management, social pressures, and unhealthy lifestyle habits such as excessive caffeine consumption, lack of physical activity, and irregular sleep-wake cycles [6,7]. These sleep

issues are often compounded by the competitive and high-pressure environment in medical colleges, where students tend to sacrifice sleep to meet academic goals. Sleep deprivation negatively impacts not just academic performance but also psychological well-being. Poor sleep has been linked to reduced alertness, impaired judgment, emotional instability, anxiety, depression, and burnout among students [8,9]. Furthermore, long-term sleep disturbances increase the risk of cardiovascular disorders, obesity, metabolic syndromes, and weakened immune responses [10]. Unfortunately, sleep health is often under-addressed in medical training programs, and many students remain unaware of sleep hygiene practices and the long-term implications of poor sleep quality.

The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) is a validated and widely used instrument to assess subjective sleep quality. It evaluates seven components—subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, duration, efficiency, disturbances, use of sleep medication, and daytime dysfunction—over the past one month [11]. A PSQI global score greater than 5 indicates poor sleep quality and is a commonly accepted threshold in sleep research.

In the Indian context, regional studies on sleep among medical students are limited, especially in Rajasthan. Udaipur, a major educational hub in southern Rajasthan, houses several medical colleges, yet there is a paucity of published literature examining sleep quality among its medical students. Identifying the prevalence and associated risk factors in this specific population is essential for developing targeted interventions and promoting mental health and academic performance.

This study was designed to assess the sleep quality among undergraduate medical students of Udaipur and to analyze the factors associated with poor sleep. The findings will help in understanding the burden of sleep-related problems in medical students and guide medical institutions to implement support systems such as sleep hygiene awareness, stress management, and academic counseling programs.

Material and Methods

Study Design and Setting: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted among undergraduate medical students in a tertiary medical college in Udaipur, Rajasthan. The study was carried out over a period of three months, from January to March 2024.

Study Population: The study population comprised MBBS students (from first to final year, including interns) currently enrolled at the selected institution. Students present during the data

collection period and willing to give informed consent were included.

Inclusion Criteria

- Undergraduate medical students (1st year to internship) enrolled at the college
- Willing to participate and provide informed consent
- Aged 18 years or above

Exclusion Criteria

- Students with diagnosed sleep disorders or psychiatric illnesses (self-reported or on treatment)
- Students taking medications known to affect sleep (e.g., sedatives, stimulants)
- Incomplete responses in the questionnaire

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was calculated using the formula for cross-sectional studies:

$$n = Z^2 \times P \times (1-P) / d^2$$

Where:

- $Z = 1.96$ (standard normal variate at 95% CI)
- $p =$ anticipated prevalence of poor sleep quality among medical students (taken as 63.8% from a previous Indian study) [12]
- $d = 7\%$ (absolute precision)

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 63.8 \times 36.2 / 7^2 = 181$$

Considering a 14% non-response rate, the final sample size was adjusted to 206.

Sampling Technique: A stratified random sampling method was used to ensure adequate representation of each academic year. The total sample was proportionately distributed among the strata (1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year Part I, 3rd year Part II, and interns).

Data Collection Tool: A pre-tested, structured, self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. It comprised the following sections:

1. Sociodemographic details – age, gender, year of study, residence (hostel/home), caffeine consumption, screen time, exercise habits, etc.
2. Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) – a standardized, validated instrument developed by Buysse et al. (1989) [11] to assess sleep quality over the past month.

The PSQI contains 19 self-rated items grouped into 7 components:

- Subjective sleep quality
- Sleep latency
- Sleep duration
- Sleep efficiency
- Sleep disturbances
- Use of sleep medication

- Daytime dysfunction

Each component is scored from 0 (no difficulty) to 3 (severe difficulty), and the global score ranges from 0 to 21.

A global PSQI score >5 indicates poor sleep quality.

Data Collection Procedure:

- The study was explained to students during lecture or clinical hours.
- Students who volunteered and met the inclusion criteria were asked to complete the questionnaire either in paper format or via a secure Google Form.
- Confidentiality was ensured, and responses were anonymized.

Ethical Considerations:

- Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.
- Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality and the option to withdraw at any point.

Data Entry and Statistical Analysis

- Data were entered into Microsoft Excel 2019 and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.
- Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize data.

- The prevalence of poor sleep quality (PSQI >5) was calculated.

Inferential statistics included:

- Chi-square test for associations between categorical variables (e.g., gender, year of study, residence).
- Independent t-test or ANOVA for continuous variables (e.g., sleep duration).
- A binary logistic regression model was used to identify independent predictors of poor sleep quality.

A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 206 undergraduate medical students participated in the study, with a response rate of 98%.

The mean age of participants was 20.4 ± 1.5 years. Of the respondents, 56.3% were female ($n = 116$) and 43.7% were male ($n = 90$).

Most students (72.3%) were residing in hostels, while the rest commuted from home. About 64.1% reported daily caffeine intake, and 81.6% admitted to using mobile phones or screens within one hour before bedtime.

Only 27.2% reported engaging in regular physical activity (≥ 3 times/week). (Table 1)

Table 1: Sociodemographic Profile of Participants (N = 206)

Variable		Frequency (n= 206)	Percentage (%)
Age (in years) (Mean \pm SD)		20.4 \pm 1.5	-
Gender	Male	90	43.7%
	Female	116	56.3%
Year of Study	1st Year	42	20.4%
	2nd Year	45	21.8%
	3rd Year Part I	38	18.4%
	3rd Year Part II	41	19.9%
	Internship	40	19.4%
Residence	Hostel	149	72.3%
	Home	57	27.7%
Caffeine Consumption		132	64.1%
Regular Physical Activity		56	27.2%
Screen Use Before Bed (>1 hr)		168	81.6%

Prevalence of Poor Sleep Quality: The mean global PSQI score among participants was 7.3 ± 3.1 , with scores ranging from 2 to 16. Based on the PSQI cut-off score of >5 , 62.6% ($n = 129$) of students were classified as having poor sleep quality. 37.4% ($n = 77$) had good sleep quality. (Table 2)

Table 2: Sleep Quality Based on Global PSQI Score

Sleep Quality	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Good Sleep (PSQI ≤ 5)	77	37.4%
Poor Sleep (PSQI > 5)	129	62.6%
Mean Global PSQI	7.3 \pm 3.1	-

Component-wise PSQI Scores: Among the seven components of PSQI, the most commonly affected domains are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Component-wise PSQI Scores

PSQI Component	Affected Students (n)	Percentage (%)
Sleep latency > 30 min	148	71.8%
Sleep duration < 6 hrs	81	39.3%
Poor subjective sleep	113	54.9%
Daytime dysfunction	139	67.4%
Sleep efficiency < 85%	88	42.7%
Use of sleep medication	10	4.8%

Factors Associated with Poor Sleep Quality: Bivariate analysis revealed significant associations between poor sleep quality and the following variables shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Factors Associated with Poor Sleep Quality (Bivariate Analysis)

Variable	Poor Sleep (%)	p-value
Female Gender	67.2%	0.04*
Screen Time >1 hour	71.4%	0.002*
No Physical Activity	73.2%	0.01*
Higher Year of Study	68.5%	0.03*
Academic Stress	74.6%	0.001*
Caffeine Consumption	64.4%	0.21

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

No statistically significant association was observed between sleep quality and age or caffeine consumption.

Multivariate Logistic Regression

A logistic regression model was applied to identify independent predictors of poor sleep quality. The following factors remained significant:

- Academic stress (Adjusted Odds Ratio [AOR] = 2.5; 95% CI: 1.4–4.6; $p = 0.002$)
- Screen time before sleep (>1 hour) (AOR = 2.1; 95% CI: 1.2–3.8; $p = 0.01$)
- Lack of physical activity (AOR = 1.9; 95% CI: 1.1–3.5; $p = 0.03$)

Discussion

This cross-sectional study assessed sleep quality among undergraduate medical students in a tertiary care institute in Udaipur using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). The findings revealed that 62.6% of the students had poor sleep quality (PSQI > 5), which is consistent with previous studies conducted among Indian medical students.

A comparable prevalence was observed in studies by Giri et al. (2013) in Maharashtra (63.8%) [12], and Panda et al. (2022) in Odisha (60.5%) [13].

This persistent pattern across different regions highlights that poor sleep is a common concern among medical students in India, likely due to the high academic demands, frequent exams, erratic schedules, and excessive screen exposure. In the current study, the most affected PSQI components were sleep latency (71.8%), daytime dysfunction

(67.4%), and subjective sleep quality (54.9%). These findings are in line with research by Patil et al. (2021) in Karnataka, which found increased sleep latency and fatigue among students with high academic stress [14].

The average global PSQI score in our study was 7.3 ± 3.1 , comparable to a mean score of 7.1 reported in a Delhi-based study by Surani et al. (2015) [15]. This score reflects moderate to poor sleep health, which, over time, can impact academic performance, mental well-being, and physical health.

Female students were found to have significantly poorer sleep quality than males, echoing findings from Gupta et al. (2016), who reported higher PSQI scores in female participants, possibly due to hormonal variations, greater anxiety, and social expectations [16].

Another important finding was the significant association of poor sleep with increased screen time before bed. More than 80% of students used mobile phones or electronic devices within one hour of sleeping. Studies have shown that screen exposure before bedtime suppresses melatonin secretion, delays sleep onset, and reduces sleep efficiency [17,18]. Academic stress and lack of physical activity were identified as independent predictors of poor sleep quality. These results are aligned with findings from studies in other medical colleges in India and abroad [19,20] Physical activity has been shown to improve sleep latency and quality through both physiological and psychological mechanisms [21].

The trend of poor sleep increased progressively across academic years, with interns reporting the highest prevalence. This observation is consistent with the study by Jain et al. (2019), which noted increasing stress and clinical workload among senior students and interns, contributing to deteriorating sleep patterns [22].

Despite caffeine consumption being reported by over 60% of participants, it did not show a statistically significant association with sleep quality in this study, possibly due to variations in sensitivity or timing of intake.

This study used a validated tool (PSQI) and employed stratified random sampling to ensure fair representation from all academic years. However, as a self-reported cross-sectional study, recall bias and social desirability bias may have affected responses. Additionally, the study was confined to one institution, limiting generalizability.

Conclusions

This study revealed a high prevalence of poor sleep quality (62.6%) among medical students in Udaipur, with significant associations observed between sleep disturbances and academic stress, increased screen time before bedtime, and lack of physical activity.

The findings underscore the urgent need to integrate sleep hygiene education and stress management programs into the medical curriculum. Institutions should promote structured schedules, regular physical activity, and awareness campaigns to mitigate screen overuse and its impact on circadian rhythms. However, as this was a cross-sectional, self-reported study conducted in a single tertiary care institution, its generalizability is limited, and the possibility of recall or reporting bias cannot be ruled out. Future longitudinal and multicentric studies are recommended to better understand causal relationships and guide targeted interventions for improving sleep health among medical students.

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